

SOCIAL SCIENCES

WELLNESS PROGRAM FOR PREVENTING AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR THROUGH JUDO PRACTICE

Anzhelina Yaneva-Prokopova

Prof., D.Sc. at Sofia University "Kliment Ohridski"

Orcid.org/0000-0002-9226-0090

Abstract

Aggressive behavior during childhood and adolescence is a growing concern across educational and public health systems worldwide. The aim of this article explores the effectiveness of a wellness program based on judo training in preventing and reducing aggressive behavior among children and adolescents. The program combines physical activity, discipline, and socio-emotional learning by practicing Judo two times weekly. The Key Findings for the experimental group showed a statistically significant reduction in aggression (−1.30 points). The control group showed a minor improvement, likely due to standard school discipline practices but without a structured behavioral intervention. Data from a pilot study are presented, along with tables of results and recommendations for future application. Based on our results analysis we are formulating concrete conclusions.

Keywords: School aggression, Prevention, Wellness program, Judo Training, children and adolescents.

1. Introduction

Aggressive behavior during childhood and adolescence is a growing concern across educational and public health systems worldwide (Dimitrova, 2017; Dimitrova, B. 2023; Tomova 2024). Defined as verbal or physical actions intended to harm or intimidate others, school aggression can manifest in forms such as bullying, physical fights, intimidation, or social exclusion (Bandura 1973; Dimitrova, 2019; Chipeva 2019; Kodokan Institute 2020; Dimitrova, B. 2020). This type of behavior often leads to serious consequences, including difficulties in emotional regulation, health imbalance, reduced academic performance, poor peer relationships, increased school dropout rates, and a higher risk of delinquency in later years (Sachs 2015; Dimitrova, B., 2017; Dimitrova, 2025; Dimitrova, B. 2025; Tomova 2024; Andonov et al. 2025). According to the World Health Organization (WHO 2022), approximately one in three students globally aged 13–15 has experienced bullying, and over 20% of students have been involved in physical fights at school. The UNESCO Global Status Report on School Violence and Bullying (2023) highlights that school-based violence affects children in nearly every country, undermining their right to education, health, and well-being. In Europe, the situation is similarly alarming. Data from the European School Survey Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) and national educational reports indicate that between 10–20% of students regularly encounter aggressive behaviors from peers in school settings. Countries such as France, Italy, and the UK have reported rising incidents of cyberbullying and physical violence in school environments, prompting nationwide anti-violence strategies. For example, the European Commission's 2024 report on adolescents focuses on key issues affecting youth in Europe, including mental health, education, and social inclusion - that over 14% of secondary students in Central and Eastern Europe report having engaged in or witnessed school fights in the previous year. These findings underline the need for innovative, holistic interventions that address

not only the behavioral symptoms of aggression (Dimitrova, 2019a; Dimitrova, 2025a; Dimitrova, B., et al. 2025; Vencislavova, 2025;). Also their root causes—such as lack of emotional regulation, social support, and structured physical outlets. In this context, physical activities with a strong pedagogical and ethical foundation, such as judo, offer promising avenues. Judo's philosophy emphasizes mutual respect, discipline, and self-improvement—values that align well with socio-emotional learning objectives (Dimitrova, N. 2019; Dimitrova, B., 2025a) When integrated into school wellness programs, judo can contribute significantly to reducing aggression while promoting empathy, cooperation, and personal responsibility among students (Dimitrova, 2020; Dimitrova, B., 2025a). The concept of the connection between body and mind originates from Japanese mythology (Kawamura et al. 2000). From a philosophical perspective, judo is considered a method of both physical and moral education, aimed at strengthening the individual's personality. Jigoro Kano, the founder of judo, emphasized that practicing this martial art offers not only physical benefits but also plays a crucial role in developing intellectual and moral qualities (Kanō 1932). The contribution of judo to education. *Journal of Health and Physical Education*, 3, 37–40, 58.). According to Kano, judo serves as a practice that fosters character development, discipline, and ethical values, which are essential for holistic personal growth (Matsumoto 1996). The rich variety of preparatory and sport-specific technical actions, each carrying different psychological demands, offers a unique opportunity—in our view—to construct a scientifically grounded system of physical education.

Methodology

Research Objective: *To examine the effect of a wellness program based on judo on:* 1. Aggression levels in children aged 10–14; 2. The level of self-control and social skills; 3. Overall psycho-emotional well-being. Two groups participated: 1. Experimental Group: 35 students who attended judo sessions twice a week, integrated with emotional self-regulation exer-

cises and group reflection. 2. Control Group: 34 students from a comparable demographic background who did not participate in the judo program.

Judo-based Wellness: Structure

The recommended training volume is 2–3 sessions per week, each lasting 45 minutes. The program introduces children to new Recreation activities and educate them on selfness and self-defense. The program benefits are: Warm-up and flexibility; Basic techniques emphasising control, respect, and partnership; Discussions on values (respect, honesty, non-violence); Breathing and relaxation exercises.

Results

✚ Educational principles

The founder of modern judo, Jigoro Kano (1860–1938), pursued a much more ambitious idea—to develop a system of “education for life.” (Jigoro Kano, 2013). This concept is illustrated through the following judo-specific principles: 1. *Shobuho*: Judo as a method of combat (technical training); 2. *Tai ikuho*: A form of physical education (development of motor skills); 3. *Shushinno*: A form of ethical education or character development; *Shushinno* involves training that is focused on independence, creative problem-solving, and the cultivation of moral qualities.

✚ Specificity of the Judo-based Wellness program

Regardless of the methods and tools used in physical education, both general and specialized training must be preceded by a preparatory phase aimed at warming up the body. In the sport of judo, this phase is given special emphasis and is known as Junbi Undo. Unlike standard warm-up routines in other sports, the judo warm-up serves broader and more holistic objectives. Junbi Undo is an ancient system of preparatory exercises (see Tab. 1).

It is more than just physical warm-up—it represents a way to elevate the fighting spirit, develop a well-conditioned body, and maintain good health. It ensures readiness, mental resilience, and vitality Junbi Undo consists of a wide variety of exercises designed to improve flexibility, motor coordination, muscle strength, heart rate regulation, breathing control, blood circulation, immune function, and the overall morale of the practitioner. We present in table format the Judo-based Wellness Program Structure. Following the logical progression in education from simple to complex, training should begin with repetitive cyclic movements performed at a steady pace, gradually transitioning to acyclic movements with variable rhythm.

Table 1.

Structure of a Judo-based Wellness Program

Section	Component	Details
I. Stances (Shizen Hontai, Migi Shizentai, Hidari Shizentai)	1. Performed individually for Center of Gravity (COG) awareness	- Enhances balance and posture awareness
	2. Against external force	a) Maintaining posture and orientation b) Yielding to neutralize external force c) Changing support: contact and distance-based
II. Locomotion	Tsugi-Ashi, Ayumi-Ashi, Tai Sabaki, Ground movements (directional variations)	- Development of mobility, body control, and spatial orientation
III. Ukemi (Breakfalls)	Mae Ukemi, Ushiro Ukemi, Yoko Ukemi, Zenpo Kaiten	- Practiced from static stances and varying heights - Executed after external impulses
IV. Kuzushi & Recovery	Balance Breaking	- Without contact - With contact
V. Games	1. Constant contact (limited support space) 2. Impact-based (“rooster fights”)	- Builds coordination, reactivity, and playful competition
VI. Osakomiyaza	Hold-down techniques	- Introduces ground control and immobilization skills
VII. Tsukuri & Kake	Set-up and Execution of Techniques	- Teaches the process of preparing for and completing throws
VIII. Imitative Practice	Tandoku Renshu (solo) Sotai Renshu (partnered): De-Ashi-Barai, O Goshi, Uki Goshi, Seoi Nage, etc.	- Develops technical precision, coordination, and memory of judo techniques

Another dimension of progression involves increasing the number of muscle groups engaged and the level of intermuscular coordination required. During the training process, focus is placed on the fundamental techniques and elements of judo, such as stances (Shizen Hontai, Migi Shizentai, Hidari Shizentai), falls (Ukemi), body movement and shifting (Tsugi-Ashi, Ayumi-Ashi, Tai Sabaki – body shifting/control), and basic throws (Nage). Techniques are taught through educational games and imitation to motivate children and

enhance their imagination and engagement. The Judo Wellness program focus is improving mind concentration, discipline, self-confidence, health balance and build anti-bullying skills.

✚ Quantitative Data Comparison

Key Findings: In table 2, the experimental group showed a statistically significant reduction in aggression (–1.30 points).

Table 2.

Changes in aggression scores before and after training in a judo program

Groupe	Aggression score before	Aggression score After	Change
Experimental	3.85	2.55	-1.30
Control	3.70	3.45	-0.25

The Belgium shows significant inclusion challenges, with over one-third of vulnerable students experiencing aggression or exclusion. Austria continues to have bullying rates slightly above the EU norm but shows promising improvements in schools using judo-

based programs. Bulgaria faces high daily incidents of school aggression, with strong evidence that cyberbullying is a major component. ol group showed a minor improvement, likely due to standard school discipline

practices but without a structured behavioral intervention experiencing aggression or exclusion. (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Change in aggression levels before and after the implementation of judo training

Belgium shows significant inclusion challenges, with over one-third of vulnerable students Austria continues to have bullying rates slightly above the EU norm but shows promising improvements in schools using judo-based programs. Bulgaria faces high daily incidents of school aggression, with strong evidence that cyberbullying is a major component. **Behavioral Patterns and Observations:** In the experimental group, students demonstrated: 1. Increased ability to de-escalate conflict; 2. Enhanced respect for authority and peers; 3. Verbalisation of emotions instead of physical retaliation. By contrast, the control group continued to display reactive behavior and unresolved peer conflicts.

Discussion

One of the key mechanisms contributing to the observed outcomes is the moral code of judo, which emphasizes mutual respect, honesty, self-control, and perseverance. Unlike many competitive sports that reward aggression and dominance, judo provides a safe and structured environment in which young people can explore physical challenge while learning to manage impulses and respect opponents. This aligns with the social-emotional learning (SEL) framework widely endorsed in European education systems. Further, the judo-based Wellness program also fostered a sense of belonging and identity, particularly among participants from vulnerable backgrounds. Students reported increased self-confidence and reduced anxiety, which are known protective factors against antisocial behavior and school dropout. Nonetheless, the study is not without limitations. The sample size was limited, and the duration of the intervention may not capture long-term behavior changes. Also, variations in coaching styles, group dynamics, and school environment may have influenced outcomes. Future research should incorporate longitudinal tracking and larger, more diverse samples across various regions and educational contexts.

Conclusion

This study affirms that wellness programs incorporating judo training can serve as effective, non-pharmacological interventions for reducing aggression in school settings. The program not only promotes physical fitness and coordination but also fosters emotional intelligence, social responsibility, and resilience—key competencies for holistic child development. The integration of judo into school curricula or extracurricular wellness initiatives offers a sustainable and scalable model for addressing behavioral challenges, especially among at-risk youth.

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